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The Percentage of Gross Domestic Expenditure on Research and Development (GERD) Financed by Businesses Globally

Has increased by +8.38% from 2013 to 2022

The variable "GERD financed by business, %" refers to the percentage of total national expenditure on research and development (R&D) that is funded by the private sector. GERD, an acronym for Gross Domestic Expenditure on Research and Development, represents the overall spending on R&D within a country, including contributions from the government, higher education institutions, non-profit organizations, and businesses. Therefore, this specific variable indicates the proportion of that total expenditure covered by investments and funds from private companies. A high percentage of GERD financed by businesses suggests a strong involvement of the private sector in promoting and developing research and innovation activities in the country.

The Percentage of Gross Domestic Expenditure on Research and Development Financed by Businesses Globally in 2022. The analysis of the percentage of GERD financed by businesses for the year 2022 reveals significant variations among different countries. This indicator is crucial for understanding the level of private sector involvement in a country's innovation and technological development, reflecting how willing businesses are to invest in R&D activities to promote economic growth and competitiveness. At the top of the ranking is Thailand, where 100% of GERD is financed by businesses. This figure is particularly noteworthy and suggests a highly dynamic and favorable environment for private investment in R&D. Following are Japan (96.9%), China (95.8%), and South Korea (94.7%), countries known for their strong technology and innovation-based economies. These high values reflect a corporate culture strongly oriented towards investment in research and development, likely supported by favorable government policies and a well-developed innovation ecosystem. The United Arab Emirates, with 91.9% of GERD financed by businesses, represents an interesting case of a rapidly evolving economy diversifying its growth sources beyond the oil sector, significantly focusing on R&D. In the United States, 82% of R&D spending is supported by the private sector, confirming the country's leadership in technological innovation, although government contribution remains significant. In Europe, Switzerland (80%), Germany (79.8%), and Belgium (79.5%) are among the countries with the highest percentages of private R&D funding. These countries have advanced economies with industrial sectors highly integrated into scientific and technological research. Sweden (77.2%) and Denmark (73.7%) also show high levels of private investment, reflecting a tradition of innovation and technological development supported by strong university-industry collaboration. Italy, with 69.2%, ranks lower than other major European economies, indicating a need for greater private sector involvement in financing R&D. However, this figure still highlights a significant commitment by Italian companies in the field of innovation, although there is room for improvement. Countries like the United Kingdom (66.3%), France (70.2%), and Finland (67.2%) show similar values, indicating a balance between public and private funding. This balance can be attributed to government policies that encourage the private sector to invest in R&D, along with strong public support for research infrastructures. In emerging and developing economies, levels of private funding are generally lower. For instance, in Brazil, only 53.8% of GERD is financed by businesses, while in South Africa it is 51.3%. These countries are still developing their innovation capacities and could benefit from policies that further incentivize private

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investments in R&D. At the bottom of the ranking are countries like Kuwait (1.2%), Mali (1%), Rwanda (0.8%), Mozambique (0.6%), Ecuador, and Paraguay (both 0.3%). These low values indicate a limited private sector participation in R&D, which can be due to various reasons, including inadequate infrastructure, unfavorable economic conditions, or limited capacity of the private sector to invest in research. In conclusion, the 2022 data analysis on the percentage of GERD financed by businesses highlights a significant disparity between countries in terms of private investment in research and development. Countries with advanced and developed technologies show high levels of private funding, while emerging and developing economies often struggle to significantly involve the private sector. This indicator is crucial for understanding the global landscape of research and development and can guide policies aimed at encouraging private investments in R&D, thereby promoting sustainable and innovative economic growth.

The Percentage of Gross Domestic Expenditure on Research and Development Financed by Businesses Globally between 2013 and 2022. The analysis of the percentage and absolute variation of GERD financed by businesses between 2013 and 2022 reveals significant trends and disparities among countries. The data shows how some countries have registered impressive increases, while others have experienced drastic declines. At the top of the list for percentage variation is El Salvador, which saw an incredible increase of 6400%, from a meager 0.60% to an impressive 39%. This significant increase can be attributed to favorable government policies, foreign investments, and a growing awareness of the importance of R&D for economic development. Paraguay also recorded a notable increase of 200%, although starting from a very low base (0.10% in 2013), reaching only 0.30% in 2022. These increases, while impressive in percentage terms, still reflect relatively low levels of private funding in R&D. Colombia saw an increase of 154.23%, from 26% to 66.10%, indicating a significant commitment from the private sector in research and development, likely supported by government incentives and greater integration into the global market. Mongolia and Cyprus both recorded significant increases of 143.90% and 143.24%, respectively, suggesting improved economic conditions and greater private sector interest in R&D. Sri Lanka, with an increase of 112.82%, shows how developing countries are increasing their efforts to involve the private sector in R&D, while Poland, with an increase of 88.86%, reflects growing economic and industrial maturity. Some Asian countries like Thailand and South Korea, already well-known for their advanced technology sectors, saw increases of 73.91% and 11.41%, respectively, further consolidating their positions as global R&D leaders. Thailand reached a remarkable 100% private funding, while South Korea almost reached 95%. In Europe, countries like Romania (52.71%), Ireland (36.80%), and Greece (35.79%) recorded significant increases, demonstrating the growing importance of the private sector in R&D. However, countries like France (10.90%) and the United Kingdom (25.81%) saw more modest increases, suggesting that public funding may still play an important role in their economies. On the other hand, some countries registered worrying decreases. The most extreme case is Uruguay, which saw a decrease of 87.72%, from 46.40% to 5.70%. Other countries like Costa Rica (-91.45%), Mali (-91.53%), and Ecuador (-96.97%) experienced dramatic declines, likely reflecting economic instability, political changes, or inadequate incentives for the private sector. Even more developed economies like Finland (-15.26%), Iceland (-19.66%), and the Czech Republic (-20.58%) saw significant decreases, suggesting potential structural challenges or changes in R&D funding priorities. Asia presents a mixed picture. While countries like China (12.97%) and Japan (7.79%) saw increases, others like Malaysia (-52.70%) experienced significant declines. The drastic decrease in Malaysia might be linked to economic or political changes that negatively affected the investment environment for R&D. In summary, the data shows a variety of trends in business-financed R&D. Countries like El Salvador, Colombia, and Thailand have made significant progress, demonstrating that adequate policies and a favorable environment can stimulate private investments. Conversely, dramatic declines in countries like Uruguay and Ecuador indicate substantial challenges that could compromise their technological and economic development. These

trends underscore the importance of a stable environment and policies that encourage the private sector to invest in R&D to promote sustainable and innovative growth.

Economic Policies to Increase Business-Financed R&D Spending. Increasing business-financed research and development (R&D) spending is crucial for stimulating innovation, economic growth, and global competitiveness. To achieve this goal, a series of targeted economic policies is necessary. Firstly, it is crucial to implement robust tax incentives, such as tax credits and specific tax deductions for R&D expenses. These incentives reduce the net cost of R&D activities for companies, making such investments more attractive. Countries like the United States and the United Kingdom have shown that such measures can be extremely effective in promoting business R&D spending. Additionally, it is important to create a favorable regulatory environment that reduces bureaucracy and simplifies the processes for obtaining R&D funding. A streamlined and transparent regulation encourages companies to undertake research projects without fear of lengthy administrative procedures. Along with this is the importance of ensuring adequate protection of intellectual property rights, so that companies can fully benefit from the fruits of their innovations. A solid system of patents and copyrights incentivizes businesses to invest in R&D, knowing that their inventions will be protected. Another key element is direct financial support through grants and subsidies. The government can allocate funds to support specific R&D projects, especially those that present a high risk or are of national strategic interest. For example, emerging sectors such as artificial intelligence, biotechnology, and renewable energy could benefit from targeted funding that further stimulates private investments. Public-private collaboration represents another powerful tool to increase R&D spending. Initiatives such as partnerships between universities and industries, technology parks, and business incubators can facilitate the sharing of knowledge, skills, and resources, creating a vibrant and productive innovation ecosystem. Investments in advanced research infrastructure, such as well-equipped laboratories and high-speed communication networks, are essential to support R&D activities. Such infrastructure not only attracts businesses but also facilitates collaboration and resource sharing among various research sector actors. Furthermore, it is essential to invest in human capital. Training and professional development programs, scholarships, and incentives for researchers can increase the number and quality of talents available for R&D activities. Through collaborations with higher education institutions, the government can ensure that curricula are aligned with labor market needs, thus preparing a highly qualified workforce for future challenges. Promoting a dynamic entrepreneurial climate is equally crucial. Creating a favorable context for innovative start-ups, with access to risk financing and a competitive market, can stimulate innovation and R&D. Governments can also facilitate access to international markets, helping companies expand their R&D activities globally. Moreover, policies aimed at improving the quality of national scientific and technological institutions can have a significant impact. Research universities of excellence and cutting-edge research centers can act as poles of attraction for talent and international investments, further stimulating R&D spending. Promoting international collaboration networks and adhering to global research programs can also increase funding and knowledge exchange opportunities. Finally, economic and political stability plays a crucial role in creating a favorable environment for R&D investments. Companies are more likely to invest in R&D in countries where economic conditions are predictable and government policies are stable and favorable to innovation. Therefore, maintaining stable and predictable macroeconomic policy, along with effective governance, can significantly influence businesses' decisions to increase R&D spending.

Conclusion. The value of business-financed R&D spending has increased for the considered countries by an amount of 44.81 units to a value of 48.56 units on average in the period between 2013 and 2022, which is an increase of +8.38%. There are countries where the value of business-financed R&D spending has grown significantly more than the period average, namely El Salvador with +6,400.00%, Paraguay with +200.00%, Colombia with +154.23%, Mongolia with +143.90%, and Cyprus with +143.24%. However, there are countries where business-financed R&D spending has decreased

significantly over the period, such as Ethiopia with -84.92%, Uruguay with -87.72%, Costa Rica with -91.45%, Mali with -91.53%, and Ecuador with -96.97%.

References

- Arnone, M., Legrande, A., Costantiello, A., & Laureti, L. (2024). *Banking Stability in the ESG Framework Across Italian Regions* (No. 121452). University Library of Munich, Germany.
- Dominick Salvatore, Cosimo Magazzino, Angelo Legrande, Alberto Costantiello, The economic determinants of world disorder events: An empirical analysis, *Journal of Policy Modeling*, 2024
- Arnone, M., & Legrande, A. (2024). *The Sustainability of the Factoring Chain in Europe in the Light of the Integration of ESG Factors* (No. 121342). University Library of Munich, Germany.
- Arnone, M., & Angelo, L. (2024). The People You Can Count on in the Italian Regions. Available at SSRN 4873511.
- Resta, E., Logroscino, G., Tafuri, S., Peter, P., Noviello, C., Costantiello, A., & Legrande, A. (2024). The Mental Health Index across the Italian Regions in the ESG Context (No. 3cztm). Center for Open Science.
- Emanuela, R., Giancarlo, L., Silvio, T., Preethymol, P., Chiara, N., Alberto, C., & Angelo, L. (2024). The Mental Health Index across the Italian Regions in the ESG Context. Available at SSRN 4865459.
- Arnone, M., & Legrande, A. (2024). *The Green Trilemma: Energy Efficiency, Banking Stability and Climate Risk in the ESG Context at World Level*. University Library of Munich, Germany.
- Arnone, M., Angelillis, B., Costantiello, A., & Legrande, A. (2024). Graduates, Training and Employment Across the Italian Regions. Available at SSRN 4850961.
- Magazzino, C., Madaleno, M., Waqas, M., & Legrande, A. (2024). Exploring the determinants of methane emissions from a worldwide perspective using panel data and machine learning analyses. *Environmental Pollution*, 348, 123807.
- Legrande, A. (2024). Companies with at least 10 Employees Selling Online across the Italian Regions (No. 120637). University Library of Munich, Germany.

- Leogrande, A. (2024). *Regular Internet Users Across the Italian Regions* (No. 120612). University Library of Munich, Germany.
- Leogrande, A. (2024). *Cultural and Creative Employment Across Italian Regions* (No. hal-04528709).
- Leogrande, A. (2024). *Knowledge Workers across the Italian Regions* (No. 4bv6a). Center for Open Science.
- Leogrande, A. (2024). *The Propensity for Patenting in the Italian Regions* (No. 120553). University Library of Munich, Germany.
- Leogrande, A. (2024). *The Innovation of the Production System in the Italian Regions* (No. 120542). University Library of Munich, Germany.
- Leogrande, A., Resta, E., & Costantiello, A. (2024). *The Renunciation of Healthcare Services in the Italian Regions in the ESG Context*. Available at SSRN 4746676.
- Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2024). *The regulatory quality in the light of environmental, social and governance framework at world level*. *Discover Global Society*, 2(1), 1.
- Resta, E., Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Anobile, F., & Leogrande, A. (2024). *The Impact of Patent Applications on Technological Innovation in European Countries*. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 28(3,), 1-15.
- Resta, E., Costantiello, A., Anobile, F., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2024). *The Opportunity Driven Entrepreneurship in the Context of Innovation Systems in Europe in the Period 2010-2019*. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP*, 28(3,), 1-13.
- Resta, E., Costantiello, A., Anobile, F., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2024). *The Impact of New Doctorate Graduates on Innovation Systems in Europe*. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 28(3,), 1-22.
- Magazzino, C. & Leogrande, A. (2024). *The Role of Air Pollution in the ESG Model at the World Level*. In C. Popescu & P. Yu (Eds.), *Intersecting Environmental Social Governance and AI for Business Sustainability* (pp. 93-122). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/979-8-3693-1151-6.ch004>
- Resta, E., Resta, O., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2024). *The hospital emigration to another region in the light of the environmental, social and governance model in Italy during the period 2004-2021*. *BMC Public Health*, 24(1), 1880.
- Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2022). *The Role of Renewable Energy Consumption in Promoting Sustainability and Circular Economy. A Data-Driven Analysis*. University Library of Munich, Germany.